

JOURNAL OF SOCIETY INNOVATION AND DEVELOPMENT

The multidisciplinary journal of society for development

JSID

www.journal.institutre.org

Supported by

JOURNAL OF SOCIETY INNOVATION AND DEVELOPMENT

The multidisciplinary journal of society for development

Journal homepage: <https://journal.institutre.org/index.php/jsid>

Analysis of Monte Lemon (Citrus Limon) and Telang Flower (Clitoria Ternatea) Herbal Tea

Zira Azifa Ayska^{1*}, Nurmahni Harahap², Halimatus Sakdiah³

^{1,2,3}MTsN 1 Banda Aceh, Indonesia

Abstract

Monte Herbal Tea is a tea made from lemon and Telang flowers, so from the combination of the two plants this herbal tea is named monte tea (lemon and Telang). In addition, this monte tea has many benefits such as increasing energy, refreshing the brain, and being able to increase body stamina. In SNI, in making this monte herbal tea I used the experimental method. Data processing is carried out by giving Monte tea that has been brewed to the panelists then after the tea has been tried the researcher starts giving the questionnaire to the panelists to fill in the appropriate statements according to the panelists regarding herbal tea as in the attachment, then after giving the questionnaire and it has been filled in by the panelists, then the researcher starts processing the data as in the research results. This tea is made from main ingredients that have many benefits for the health of the body. Such as lemon fruit that can contribute Vitamin C to our body, and Telang flowers that can reduce the risk of hypertension and heart disease. In this study there are several elements that were tested, namely, color, texture, aroma, and taste. In this study requires panelists totaling 10 people.

Keyword: Tea; Palm; Lemon; Telang flower

* Corresponding author, email: ziraazifa2008@gmail.com

Received 24 January 2024; Received in revised form 23 February 2024; Accepted 1 April 2024; Available online 04 May 2024

<https://doi.org/>

Page 215-225

© Published by Journal of Society Innovation and Development. This is an open access article under the CC BY-SA 4.0 license (<https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by-sa/4.0/>).

INTRODUCTION

Tea plants (*Camellia sinensis*) have the potential to be antibacterial because they contain bioactives, one of which is tannin. Tea plants have been widely recognized by the world population as beverage ingredients or as herbal medicines that are quite easy for the community to obtain. The benefits of tea include a substance that can help us increase immunity. This substance is vitamin C, which is very active and helps boost our immune system. This helps us to be able to avoid various diseases. Tea is also widely used as a medicine to treat headaches (Cristina, 2024; Munidar, 2024; Paull, 2024; Rahmadani, 2024).

Lemon (*Citrus limon*) is a type of citrus whose fruit is commonly used for flavoring and refreshment in many of the world's culinary arts. The tree is medium-sized, can usually reach 6 m, grows in tropical and sub-tropical climates, and cannot stand cold weather. Some of the benefits of lemon are: it boosts the immune system; it is good for the brain; it balances the body's pH; it supports heart health; it can control body weight; it protects the body from anemia; it improves digestive health; it refreshes the breath; and it is good for the liver.

Telang flower (*Clitoria ternatea*) is one type of plant that is usually found in people's yards and can be used as a cultivated plant. This plant mostly has dazzling blue, white, pink, and purple colors. This flower can also be used for various purposes, for example, for food coloring, cakes, and as an ingredient that can be used for making drinks. Telang flowers are often known to have many benefits for the body (Rahman, 2023; Tiara, 2022; Misbah, 2019; Aziz, 2023; Rudi, 2021). Telang flowers can be used for drinks made directly from flowers that have just been picked from the plant, or they can also be used in the initial process by drying the plant and then blending it with warm water. This tea does not have the aroma of tea in general, but it has a very distinctive aroma, like the aroma of grass. Some other benefits of bayang flowers are: good for the brain; Can improve mood, It prevents hair loss, stimulates hair growth, reduces inflammation, and reduces the risk of hypertension and heart disease.

Making this herbal tea using lemon and telang flowers is one of the teas that is beneficial for the health of the body. In addition to being beneficial for health, this herbal tea also makes it easier for people if they want to make it because it is made from plants that we easily find in our daily environment.

From the background of the problems that have been made, it can be concluded that the objectives of this study are: to determine the analysis of herbal teabags of lemon (*Citrus limon*) and telang flower (*Clitoria ternatea*). The expected benefits of this analysis are theoretically: as a motivation for the people of Indonesia to continue to make creations from materials that are around us or from materials that are typically owned in our area. Practically: To make it easier for Indonesian people to get cheap and affordable herbal medicines.

No	Research	Similarities	Differences
1.	Title: Assessment of Antioxidant Capacity and Sensory Acceptability of Dragon Fruit Peel (Pitaya Fruit) Teabag with the Addition of Lemon Peel and Stevia. Researcher Name: Atik Shofiati, M.A.M. Andriani, and Choirul Anam. Published: Journal of Food Technoscience, Vol.	Tea making	Using dragon fruit peel, lemon peel and stavia.

3, No. 2, April 2014. Research Results: Total phenolics, total betacyanin, and DPPH free radical scavenging activity of dragon fruit peel teabags decreased as the concentration of lemon peel added increased. The addition of lemon peel had a significant effect on total phenol content, betacyanin content, and DPPH free radical scavenging activity in the teabags produced.

2. Title: Effect of Comparison of Black Tea (*Camellia sinensis*) and Red Ginger (*Zingiber officinale* var. *Rubrum*) on the Characteristics of Teabag. Researcher Name: Komang Ayu Melinda Savitri, I Wayan Rai Widarta, Anak Agung Gede Ngurah Anom Jambe. Published: Journal of Food Science and Technology, Vol. 8, No. 4, 419-429, December 2019. Research Results: The comparison of black tea and red ginger had a very significant effect on moisture content, total phenols, flavonoids, antioxidant activity, color (hedonic), aroma (scoring), taste (scoring), had a significant effect on juice content and aroma (hedonic), and had no significant effect on taste (hedonic) or overall acceptance (hedonic).

3. Title: Making Herbal Tea from Moringa Leaves to Increase Endurance During the COVID-19 Pandemic in Limo District. Name of researcher: Maryam Nadya Britany, Lilik Sumarni. Published: National Seminar on Community Service 2020, Muhammadiyah University Jakarta, October 7, 2020 Research Results: Moringa leaf tea is one of the alternative herbal medicines to increase body immunity during a pandemic like today. Consuming

moringa leaves is a preventive effort to avoid viruses and diseases. In addition, the socialization of making tea from moringa leaves is considered less effective when done online because you cannot directly see the process and final results of making tea from moringa leaves. The rest of the videos that have been uploaded have received positive responses from YouTube account users and residents of the complex where the tutorial was held.

- | | | |
|---|------------|-------------------------|
| <p>4. Title: Assistance for Rose Tea Packaging to Realize Sustainable Entrepreneurship in Clutang Village, Central Java Province. Researcher Name: Yustina Wuri Wulandari, Vivi Nuraini Published: November 2020. Research Results: Putri Mawar SMEs have been able to create and apply attractive product packaging in packaging rose tea so that quality tea products are produced and able to compete in the market.</p> | Tea making | Using roses |
| <p>5. Title: Optimization of Dragon Fruit Peel (<i>Hylocereus polyrhizus</i>) Tea Processing. Researcher Name: Mukhti Ali. Published: January-June 2016. Research Results: Shows that there is a significant effect of dragon fruit type on antioxidant content and antioxidant activity at the 5% real level. While the drying method does not have a different effect on antioxidant levels or antioxidant activity,.</p> | Tea making | Using dragon fruit peel |
-

The results of research (Irma Zarwinda, Training in Making Healthy Drink Telang Lemonade, 2023) with the title Training in Making Healthy Drink Telang Lemonade. Concluding that the level of knowledge of students and female students about the healthy drink telang lemonade is low, namely 61.875%, this training must be carried out so that students and female students get more information about the properties and uses of telang flowers, while the

level of satisfaction of students and female students of SMK Farmasi Cut Mutia Kota Banda Aceh towards this activity is 100%, which means it is very high.

The results of research (Titi Mutiara Kiranawati, 2022) with the title Effect of Carrageenan and Lemon Ratio on Antioxidant Activity and Physical Properties of Telang Flower Jelly Drink. Summarizing that the concentration of carrageenan and lemon added more and more, the antioxidant activity and viscosity obtained more and more, the presence of lemon and carrageenan can affect the physical properties of telang flower juice jelly drink products.

The results of research (Fais Wahidatul Arifatin, 2021) with the title Training in Making Modern Drinks from Telang Flowers for PKK Mothers in Solokuro Village. It concluded that from this modern beverage-making training activity, which was carried out in August 2021 with 62 PKK mothers in Solokuro village, it was found that many residents did not know the use of telang flowers and various kinds of processed drinks whose main ingredient was telang flowers. The results of research (Azizah Niken Ayu Widowati A. M., 2021) with the title. Effect of Lemon Fruit Peel Addition (*Citrus limon* L.) Dry on Organoleptic Characteristics, Total Dissolved Solids, pH, Vitamin C Content, and Total Phenols of Moringa Leaf (*Moringa oleifera*) Teabag. It was concluded that adding dried lemon peel can significantly affect ($P < 0.05$) the total soluble solids, pH, and organoleptic characteristics of the color attribute. Moringa leaf teabag without added dried lemon peel (T1) gave the best results with a total soluble solids value of 0.18%, a pH value of 7.84, a vitamin C content of 1756.26 mg/100 g, a total phenol content of 68.04 mg/gallat, and a color of yellowish green.

METHOD

The research method used in this research is the experimental method. According to Sugiyono (2015), experimental research is research conducted to seek the effect of certain treatments on others under controlled conditions. Stages in experimental research include collecting, preparing, and making herbal tea and testing tea products based on the table of dry tea requirements according to standard 7 SNI 3836:2013, namely the test of the state of steeping water (color, smell, taste) with typical requirements for tea products.

The organoleptic assessment is used to assess the quality of herbal tea products. According to Chondro Suryono (2018), an organoleptic test or sensory test is a testing method that uses the human senses as the main tool for measuring the acceptance of the product. Furthermore, each panelist is given one herbal tea bag to try. And next, the panelists were given a questionnaire, and then the panelists filled out the Monte herbal tea efficacy questionnaire with a Likert scale. Which consists of positive statements: SS = 3, S = 2, TS = 1, and negative statements: SS = 1, S = 2, TS = 3. Furthermore, the researchers conducted open interviews about the panelists' responses to the presence of monte lemon (*Citrus limon*) and bay flower (*Clitoria ternatea*) herbal tea. Furthermore, the researcher conducted an open interview about the panelists' responses about the color, smell, and taste of monte lemon (*Citrus limon*) herbal tea (*Clitoria ternatea*). Data collection tools in the following research are:

- Organoleptic test questionnaire
- Open interview guidelines

Data processing methods are carried out by giving Monte tea that has been brewed to the panelists. After the tea has been tried, the researcher starts giving the questionnaire to the panelists to fill in the appropriate statements according to the panelists regarding herbal tea, as in the attachment. After giving the questionnaire and having been filled in by the panelists, the

researcher starts processing the data as in the research results. Analyze the data in this study using the percentage formula with the equation:

$$P = \frac{FN}{N} \times 100\%$$

(Sudijono, 2018)

Description:

P = Percentage number

F = Frequency of Monte herbal tea efficacy questionnaire scores

N = Number of panelists

Therefore, the analysis carried out in this study is a percentage calculation with an organoleptic test with a hedonic scale on Monte tea brew with taste, aroma, and color and texture parameters.

FINDING AND DISCUSSION

Finding

This tea is made from main ingredients that have many benefits for the health of the body. Such as lemon fruit, which can contribute Vitamin C to our body, and telang flowers, which can reduce the risk of hypertension and heart disease. In this study, several elements were tested, namely, color, texture, aroma, and taste. In this study requires panelists totaling 10 people. The following research results are presented in the table below:

Table 1. Percentage of Monte Tea Color

Color			
Answer	Total Answer	Answer Score	Percentage
SS	9	27	90
S	1	2	10
TS	0	0	0

Based on Table 4.1 above, it can be explained that the color of monte tea is much liked and has a percentage of SS = 90%, S = 10%, and TS = 0%. Furthermore, the results of the Monte Tea Flavor Percentage are in the following table:

Table 2. Percentage of Monte Tea Texture

Texture			
Answer	Total Answer	Answer Score	Percentage
SS	7	21	70
S	3	6	30
TS	0	0	0

Based on Table 4.2 above, it can be explained that the texture of monte tea is much liked and has a percentage of SS = 70%, S = 30%, and TS = 0%. Furthermore, the results of the Monte Tea Aroma Percentage are in the following table:

Table 3. Percentage of Monte Tea Aroma

Answer	Aroma		
	Total Answer	Answer Score	Percentage
SS	3	9	30
S	6	12	60
TS	1	1	10

Based on Table 4.3 above, it can be explained that the aroma of monte tea is much liked and has a percentage of SS = 30%, S = 60%, and TS = 10%. Furthermore, the results of the Monte Tea Flavor Percentage are in the following table:

Table 4. Percentage of Monte Tea Flavor

Answer	Flavor		
	Total Answer	Answer Score	Percentage
SS	4	12	40
S	6	12	60
TS	0	0	0

Based on the table above, it can be explained that the taste of monte tea is much liked and has a percentage of SS = 40%, S = 60%, and TS = 0%.

Discussion

From the results of the research that has been done, there are many positive statements. Apart from having a distinctive color, aroma, and taste, monte herbal tea is rich in health benefits. The results of the analysis of monte herbal tea show that the aroma of monte tea has a percentage of SS = 30%, S = 60%, and TS = 10%. The taste of monte tea has a percentage of SS = 40%, S = 60%, and TS = 10%. Color in monte tea has a percentage of SS = 90%, S = 10%, and TS = 0%. The texture of monte herbal tea has a percentage of SS = 70%, S = 30%, and TS = 0%. This research is in line with research (Noriko, 2013), which states that tea plants contain bioactive tannins, so these plants have potential as antibacterials because one of the benefits of tannins is that they are antibacterial.

Furthermore, this research is in line with research (Saragih, 2014), which says that the interaction of temperature and drying time has a very significant effect on the level of liking of the color of Torbangun leaf tea, so it is necessary to conduct a DMRT further test to determine the effect of the interaction of temperature and drying time on the color of Torbangun leaf tea. Furthermore, this research is in line with research (Komang Ayu Melinda Savitri, 2019), which states that tea drinks are drinks made by brewing tea plants that have been dried beforehand and are taken from the leaves, leaf tops, or petioles. Furthermore, this research is in line with research (Bambang Sigit Amanto T. N., 2019), which states that processed tea from plants that are not included in the plant (*Camellia sinensis*) is also called herbal tea.

Furthermore, this research is in line with research (Zjahra Vianita Nugraheni, 2022), which states that in tea drinks there is usually a bitter or fast taste caused by tannin compounds. In addition to tannins, catechin compounds can also cause an astringent taste in tea because

catechin compounds still include derivatives of tannin compounds. Furthermore, this research is in line with research (Irma Zarwinda, Training in Making Healthy Drink Telang Lemonade, 2023), which states that telang flowers have many benefits and there are still many who have not utilized telang flowers in processing healthy foods and drinks. In this study, lemon juice is also used, which is able to increase the efficacy of telang flower healthy drinks. Furthermore, this research is in line with research (Ali Ikhwan, 2022), which states that telang flowers have many benefits for the body. This plant can be used as a drink that is processed directly from freshly picked flowers without having to be dried first. However, it can also be used after drying and then blending with warm water. Telang flower tea has a very distinctive aroma, which is like the aroma of grass.

Furthermore, this research is in line with research (Azizah Niken Ayu Widowati A. M., 2022), which states that tea is a drink that is good for the human body and can be enjoyed by brewing. Making tea does not have to be from plants that contain whole tea leaves; it can come from a mixture of tea or from herbal plants (herbal tea). Furthermore, this research is in line with research (Alfian Hendra Krisnawan R. B., 2017), which states that lemon fruit contains natural antioxidants because it contains vitamin C, citric acid, essential oils, bioflavonoids, polyphenols, coumarins, flavonoids, and volatile oils on its skin, such as limonene ($\pm 70\%$).

CONCLUSION

Monte tea is a tea derived from lemon fruit plants and Telang flowers. This is one of the teas that is a variation of herbal tea in general because it is made from mixed plants, namely lemon fruit and Telang flowers, which are easily obtained by Indonesians. Besides that, this tea is also rich in benefits and can increase the immunity of the human body. And this tea is one of the alternative medicines made from natural ingredients without being made from chemicals. And based on the results and discussion, it can be concluded that the conclusion of this monte herbal tea research is that this tea is much liked because it has a delicious color and taste and a unique aroma. Panelist assessment of the taste of tea is done by observing the taste using the sense of taste (tongue), then assessing the panelist's preference in the form of a scale of preference felt when tasting tea.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

- Alfian Hendra Krisnawan, R. B. (2017). *POTENSI ANTIOKSIDAN EKSTRAK KULIT DAN PERASAN DAGING BUAH LEMON (Citrus Lemon) LOKAL DAN IMPOR*. Prosiding Seminar Nasional 2017 Fakultas Pertanian UMJ, 31.
- Ali Ikhwan, S. H. (2022). *Pemanfaatan Teh Bunga Telang (Clitoria Ternatea) sebagai Minuman Kesehatan dan Meningkatkan UMKM di Masa Pandemi Covid 19 kepada Masyarakat di Desa Simonis Kecamatan Aek Natas*. Pendidikan Tambusa, 2.
- Azizah Niken Ayu Widowati, A. M. (2021). Pengaruh Penambahan Kulit Buah Lemon (Citrus limon (L.)) Kering Terhadap Karakteristik Organoleptik, Total Padatan Terlarut, pH, Kandungan Vitamin C dan Total Fenol Teh Celup Daun Kelor (Moringa oleifera). *Teknologi Pangan*, 30.

- Azizah Niken Ayu Widowati, A. M. (2022). Pengaruh Penambahan Kulit Buah Lemon (*Citrus limon* (L.)) Kering Terhadap Karakteristik Organoleptik, Total Padatan Terlarut, pH, Kandungan Vitamin C dan Total Fenol Teh Celup Daun Kelor (*Moringa oleifera*). *Teknologi Pangan*, 30.
- Azizi, A. (2023). People's Views on Stereotypes of Pidie and Padang Communities. *Journal of Society Innovation and Development (JSID)*, 5(1), 101-115.
- Bambang Sigit Amanto, T. N. (2019). PENGARUH LAMA BLANCHING DAN RUMUS PETIKAN DAUN TERHADAP KARAKTERISTIK FISIK, KIMIA, SERTA SENSORIS TEH DAUN TIN (*Ficus carica*). *Jurnal Teknologi Hasil Pertanian*, 2.
- Chondro Suryono, L. N. (2018). Uji Kesukaan dan Organoleptik Terhadap 5 kemasan dan Produk Kepulauan Seribu Secara Deskriptif. *Pariwisata*, 96.
- Cristina, G. (2024). The Acehese Folklore and Social Behavior. *JOURNAL OF ACEH STUDIES (JOAS)*, 1(1), 51-60.
- Fais Wahidatul Arifatin, I. A. (2021). PELATIHAN PEMBUATAN MINUMAN MODERN DARI BUNGA TELANG UNTUK IBU PKK DESA SOLOKURO. *Pengabdian Nasional*, 54.
- Ibrahi, A. (2024). The Teumatok Culture in Aceh Singkil. *JOURNAL OF ACEH STUDIES (JOAS)*, 1(1), 1-8.
- Irma Zarwinda, R. A. (2023). Pelatihan Pembuatan Healthy Drink Telang Lemonade. *Pengabdian Kepada Masyarakat*, 99.
- Irma Zarwinda, R. A. (2023). Pelatihan Pembuatan Healthy Drink Telang Lemonade. *Pengabdian Kepada Masyarakat*, 101.
- Komang Ayu Melinda Savitri, I. W. (2019). PENGARUH PERBANDINGAN TEH HITAM (*Camellia sinensis*) DAN JAHE MERAH (*Zingiber officinale* var. *Rubrum*) TERHADAP KARAKTERISTIK TEH CELUP. *Jurnal Ilmu dan Teknologi Pangan*, 419.
- Misbah, T. L. (2019). Intercultural Communication: Acculturation, Assimilation and Problems. *Journal of Society Innovation and Development (JSID)*, 1(1), 16-20.
- Munidar, F. (2024). The Acehese Literature and Social Behavior. *JOURNAL OF ACEH STUDIES (JOAS)*, 1(1), 31-40.
- Noriko, N. (2013). Potensi Daun Teh (*Camellia sinensis*) dan Daun Ating-ating *Acalypha indica* L. dalam Menghambat Pertumbuhan *Salmonella typhi*. *Jurnal AL-AZHAR INDONESIA SERI SAINS DAN TEKNOLOGI*, 105.
- Paull, J. (2024). The Impact of Coffee Shops on Aceh's Economic Sustainability. *JOURNAL OF ACEH STUDIES (JOAS)*, 1(1), 41-50.

- Rahmadani, A. (2024). The Writing Culture of Scholars of The Aceh kingdom. *JOURNAL OF ACEH STUDIES (JOAS)*, 1(1), 9-20.
- Rahman, F. (2023). Caregiver's Interpersonal Communication Approach to The Elderly. *Journal of Society Innovation and Development (JSID)*, 5(1), 116-123.
- Rudi, D. A., Wijaya, T. S. I., & Murdani, T. (2021). Socio-Economic Correlation of Scavenger Community in Religious Life. *Journal of Society Innovation and Development (JSID)*, 3(1), 16-20.
- Saragih, R. (2014). UJI KESUKAAN PANELIS PADA TEH DAUN TORBANGUN (COLEUS AMBOINICUS). *E-Journal WIDYA Kesehatan Dan Lingkungan*, 46-52.
- Sugiyono. (2015). *Metodologi Penelitian Kuantitatif, Kualitatif, dan R&D*. Sugiyono. 2018. *Metodologi Penelitian Kuantitatif, Kualitatif, dan R&D*. Bandung: Alfabeta, 107.
- Tiara, A. (2022). Society: Solutions for Building Ethics Communication on Social Media. *Journal of Society Innovation and Development (JSID)*, 3(2), 013-017.
- Titi Mutiara Kiranawati, R. R. (2022). PENGARUH RASIO KARAGENAN DAN LEMON TERHADAP AKTIVITAS ANTIOKSIDAN DAN SIFAT FISIK JELLY DRINK BUNGA TELANG. *Agroindustri*, 30.
- Zjhra Vianita Nugraheni, T. M. (2022). Ekstraksi Senyawa Fenolat dalam Daun Teh Hijau (*Camellia sinensis*). *Akta Kimia Indonesia*, 70.